

A Comparative Analysis of Disposable Syringes vs. Multi-Use Dental Syringes for Vasectomy Procedures: Feasibility and Cost Implications

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Abstract:

This study compares the use of disposable plastic syringes with lignocaine 2% plain versus multi-use dental syringes with cartridge lignocaine and adrenaline for no-scalpel vasectomy (NSV). The use of adrenaline in dental cartridges was necessitated by the unavailability of plain lignocaine in this format. Despite theoretical benefits such as reduced waste and quicker preparation times, significant clinical and financial barriers were identified. These findings suggest that disposable syringes and needles remain the more practical and cost-effective option for high-volume vasectomy clinics.

Introduction:

Vasectomy is a permanent and effective method of male contraception, with the no-scalpel vasectomy (NSV) technique widely preferred due to its minimally invasive nature and reduced complication rates (Sanchez and Riley, 2014). Local anaesthesia plays a key role in minimising patient discomfort during the procedure. In our practice, lignocaine 2% plain is typically used, administered via disposable plastic syringes with a 27-gauge needle. However, given the high volume of procedures we perform, we explored switching to multi-use dental syringes with pre-loaded cartridges to improve efficiency.

The primary goal of this study is to evaluate the clinical feasibility and cost implications of using multi-use dental syringes with lignocaine and adrenaline cartridges, compared to the standard disposable plastic syringes and needles with plain lignocaine. Due to the lack of plain lignocaine in dental cartridges, we trialled the adrenaline-containing alternative. This study also considers the potential risks associated with adrenaline use and evaluates whether the proposed change offers tangible benefits for high-volume clinics.

Methods:

Our current practice involves using 2% plain lignocaine, with 5 ml split between two 2.5 ml syringes. (Image 1 and 2) The anaesthetic is administered using a 27-gauge, 13 mm needle, which is commonly used in vasectomy procedures due to its balance between effective anaesthesia and minimal patient discomfort.

In our trial, we explored the use of multi-use dental syringes with pre-loaded 2.2 ml cartridges of lignocaine with adrenaline (1:80,000). (Image 3 and 4) Two cartridges were used per procedure, and the dental syringes were sterilised for re-use. The trial compared both approaches based on:

- Ease of use and preparation time
- Risk of complications, including intraoperative and delayed bleeding
- Cost per procedure, including the investment required for dental syringes and ongoing cartridge use
- Operational efficiency in a high-volume clinic setting

Image 1 and 2 - 3ml Luer Lock Syringe and 27g 13mm needle

Image 3 and 4 - Dental Syringe, 2.2ml 2% Lignocaine with Adrenaline, 30g dental needle

Results:

The use of multi-use dental syringes presented several challenges. First, the lack of availability of plain lignocaine in dental cartridges meant that adrenaline was included in all cases. According to the AUA guidelines (2012), adrenaline has the potential to mask intraoperative bleeding, which may result in delayed hematoma formation after the procedure. Although adrenaline can reduce bleeding during surgery, this presents a risk when it comes to identifying and controlling bleeding on the operating table.

Preparation time with the dental syringes was faster, as expected, due to the pre-loaded cartridges, which eliminated the need to manually draw up the anaesthetic. However, the difficulties encountered with the smaller 30-gauge dental needles, compared to the 27-gauge needles used in our standard practice, impacted the ease of administration.

Cost Analysis:

The financial impact of switching to multi-use dental syringes was a significant factor. The cost analysis is summarised as follows:

- **Disposable Syringes and Needles Approach:**
 - Lignocaine 2% (5 ml per case): AUD \$1.29
 - Syringes (3 ml, Luer lock, 2 per case): AUD \$0.22
 - Needles (27 gauge, 13 mm, 2 per case): AUD \$0.12
 - Total per case (including 20% waste): AUD \$1.96
- **Multi-Use Dental Syringe Approach:**
 - Lignocaine 2% + Adrenaline (2.2 ml cartridges, 2 per case): AUD \$2.72
 - Dental Needle (30 gauge short, 1 per case): AUD \$0.16
 - Total per case: AUD \$2.88

The cost per case for the dental syringe method was AUD \$0.92 higher than the traditional method, which over the course of 8,000 procedures annually results in an additional expense of AUD \$7,360. This does not include the initial investment required for purchasing the multi-use dental syringes, estimated at approximately USD \$2,000.

Discussion:

The theoretical advantages of the dental syringe method, including reduced waste and quicker preparation time, were offset by several clinical and practical drawbacks. The use of adrenaline, necessary due to the unavailability of plain lignocaine in dental cartridges, raised concerns about the potential for delayed bleeding and hematoma formation, in line with findings from the AUA guidelines (2012). Furthermore, the difficulty of using smaller dental needles introduced challenges during administration, and the increased cost per case made this approach less feasible for high-volume clinics.

Previous studies, such as Shih et al. (2010), demonstrated that smaller gauge needles can reduce patient discomfort. However, in our trial, the benefits of using smaller needles did not

outweigh the increased clinical risks associated with adrenaline and the operational challenges posed by the dental syringes.

Conclusion: Switching from disposable syringes and needles to multi-use dental syringes with lignocaine and adrenaline cartridges does not offer significant benefits for vasectomy procedures. The increased cost, difficulty with needle handling, and the potential for delayed postoperative complications due to adrenaline outweigh the minor efficiency gains. For high-volume vasectomy clinics, the continued use of disposable syringes with plain lignocaine remains the most practical and cost-effective choice, in line with the recommendations of the AUA guidelines.

References:

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